

STIFFNESS EVALUATION OF THE COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH WAVY PLYS AND THEIR STABILITY ANALYSIS

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1 Introduction

Creation of the ply waviness during different composite fabrication processes is a critical issue for the analysis of the composite structures. It is a source of geometrical non-uniformity which makes the composite analysis and modeling complicated and computation-intensive. For simplicity, when analyzing laminated composites, idealized lamina with perfectly straight fibers is often assumed. However, the waviness usually produces different mechanical properties for such laminates [1-8]. Ply waviness could be either the outcome of the local deformation of the fibers, or be caused by the residual stresses accumulated during the curing process. It usually happens through the thickness of the composite parts and can be often revealed by their destructive inspection.

Several researchers have introduced different theories, micro-mechanical finite element methods (M-FEM) and experimental techniques to investigate the elastic behavior of composite laminates having ply waviness. Lin *et al.* [9] developed a formulation to predict the compressive failure of the composite laminates with wavy fibers and a nonlinear matrix. Wisnom *et al.* [10] discussed the effect of the misalignment angle between the fibers and the loading axis and showed that small misalignment angles have a very strong effect on compressive strength. Camponeschi *et al.* [11] designed an interface measurement technique using an optical microscope equipped with an x-z indexing table to measure waviness at the mid-plane of the laminate and then analyzed and established a theoretical relationship between fiber waviness and reduction of compressive strength. Lo *et al.* [12] developed a model to predict the compressive strength of composite laminates using a combined analytical and semi-empirical approach. In the tension case, Rai *et al.* [13] and Chan *et al.* [14] investigated the effect of fiber waviness on stiffness of composites by a numerical method. Bogetti *et al.* [15,16], developed an analytical model for evaluating the

stiffness reduction of a laminate having waviness. However, no explicit analytical formulation was obtained in their model. Garnich *et al.* [17], developed an incremental scheme to predict the general stress-strain response for a curved fiber composite lamina. Chun *et al.* [18], evaluated the influence of in-plane waviness on the structural response and its sensitivity on a composite beam. Ray *et al.* [19] and Reddy *et al.* [20] developed finite element micromechanical models for stiffness of composite plates having waviness.

The main objective of this paper is to present explicit formulas to evaluate the influence of the out-of-plane fiber waviness on the stiffness of the composite panels. Stability sensitivities due to the variation of fiber waviness would also be assessed by determination of their effects on the critical buckling loads of the composite laminates under compression and shear. Our proposed approach to the problem of waviness is to calculate the equivalent homogenized properties of the composite laminate under consideration, and subsequently use these properties for structural analysis. Results of the developed method are compared with those of M-FEM of Garnich *et al.* [17]. Next, the effects of the ply waviness on the buckling behavior of the composite laminates under compression and pure shear are investigated with two different Finite Element Model (FEM) approaches which would be presented in details in the following section. Finally, the results are compared with those of analytical solutions.

2 Effective Mechanical Properties

2.1 Analytical Formulation

The cross section of a monolithic laminate with local ply waviness has been shown in Fig. 1. To obtain the reduced stiffness values, the average strain values over the length of the laminate should be calculated.

Fig. 1. Laminate configuration with ply waviness

The stress-strain relation in XZ coordinate system is defined as [21],

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [\bar{S}] \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$[\varepsilon]$ and $[\sigma]$ are the strain and stress tensors, respectively, and $[\bar{S}]$ is the compliance matrix which is defined as,

$$[\bar{S}] = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} & \bar{S}_{12} & \bar{S}_{16} \\ \bar{S}_{21} & \bar{S}_{22} & \bar{S}_{26} \\ \bar{S}_{16} & \bar{S}_{26} & \bar{S}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}_{11} &= S_{11}\zeta^4 + (2S_{12} + S_{66})\zeta^2\xi^2 + S_{22}\xi^4 \\ \bar{S}_{12} = \bar{S}_{21} &= (S_{11} + S_{22} - S_{66})\zeta^2\xi^2 \\ &+ S_{12}(\zeta^4 + \xi^4) \\ \bar{S}_{22} &= S_{11}\xi^4 + (2S_{12} + S_{66})\zeta^2\xi^2 + S_{22}\zeta^4 \\ \bar{S}_{16} = \bar{S}_{61} &= (2S_{11} - 2S_{12} - S_{66})\zeta^3\xi \\ &- (2S_{22} - 2S_{12} - S_{66})\zeta\xi^3 \\ \bar{S}_{26} = \bar{S}_{62} &= (2S_{11} - 2S_{12} - S_{66})\zeta\xi^3 \\ &- (2S_{22} - 2S_{12} - S_{66})\zeta^3\xi \\ \bar{S}_{66} &= 2(2S_{11} + 2S_{22} - 4S_{12} - S_{66})\zeta^2\xi^2 \\ &+ S_{66}(\zeta^4 + \xi^4). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here, $\zeta = \cos\theta$, $\xi = \sin\theta$ and θ is the angle between the fiber and direction X throughout the laminate and

$$S_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} , ν_{21} and G_{12} are the stiffness properties of the lamina, $i, j = 1, 2, 6$.

Now if we assume the fiber waviness as a sinusoidal function that its amplitude is reducing linearly from h_{max} to zero at the extreme plies, we can assume the out-of-plane fiber waviness as:

$$w(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2|z|}{t} \right) h_{max} \sin \frac{2\pi x}{l_w} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\left(1 - \frac{2|z|}{t} \right) \frac{\pi h_{max}}{l_w} \cos \frac{2\pi x}{l_w} \right) \quad (6)$$

h_{max} and l_w are the maximum waviness height and length over all the laminate plies. t is the laminate thickness. Therefore the equivalent values for the compliance matrix could be written as:

$$\bar{S}_{eqij} = \frac{1}{Lt} \int_{-\frac{t}{2}}^{\frac{t}{2}} \int_0^L \bar{S}_{ij} dx dz \quad (7)$$

and the equivalent major Young's modulus would be obtained as:

$$E_x = \left((1 - \mu) S_{11} + \mu (S_{11} \Xi_1 + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \Xi_2 + S_{22} \Xi_3) \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where $\mu = l_w/L$ is the waviness fraction and

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi_1 &= \frac{1}{t} \sum_{i=1}^N (1 + \eta_i^2 / 2) (1 + \eta_i^2)^{-3/2} t_i \\ \Xi_2 &= \frac{1}{t} \sum_{i=1}^N \eta_i^2 / 2 (1 + \eta_i^2)^{-3/2} t_i \\ \Xi_3 &= \frac{1}{t} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(1 - (1 + 3\eta_i^2 / 2) (1 + \eta_i^2)^{-3/2} \right) t_i \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

N and t_i are the total number of laminate plies and thickness of the i^{th} ply respectively; and

$\eta_i = \frac{\pi}{l_w} \left(1 - \frac{2|z|}{t} \right) h_{\max}$. All other effective laminate properties could be obtained in the similar manner.

2.2 Evaluation of the Laminate Stiffness

To validate the formulations obtained in the previous section, the stiffness results are compared with those of finite element micromechanics modeling done by Garnich *et al.* [17]. In their study, the waviness was assumed to be sinusoidal. Based on the volume percentage of each constituent, the wavelength and the amplitude of the waved fibers, the unit cell geometry was defined (see Fig. 2). This unit cell was divided into hexahedral finite elements as shown in Fig. 3. In order to determine the stiffness parameters, stress analysis of the wavy unit cell was carried out for several independent load cases.

Here we consider the same fiber and matrix properties of a graphite/epoxy system as were employed by Garnich *et al.* [17]. The fiber is assumed to have transversely isotropic elastic properties of $E_1 = 207.5$ GPa, $E_2 = E_3 = 25$ GPa, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 95$ GPa, $G_{23} = 9.2$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.24$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.359$. The polymer matrix is assumed to have isotropic elastic properties of $E = 4.5$ GPa and $\nu = 0.34$. For 40, 50, 60, and 70% of fiber volume fractions (V_f/V), the predicted equivalent major Young's modulus is shown in Fig. 4. As it can be seen the modulus values obtained from Eq. (8) are in close agreement with those of complex M-FEM results of Garnich *et al.* [17].

Fig. 2. A wavy fiber unit cell volume [17]

Fig. 3. M-FEM discretization of part of the unit cell [17]

Fig. 4. Major modulus (E_1) as a function of waviness

3 Buckling of Composite Panels with Wavy Plies

3.1 Compression Case

3.1.1 Analytical Formulation

In this section, we consider a rectangular composite plate having a region with wavy plies (see Fig. 5). We are specifically interested to see if it is a valid assumption to consider the effects of the ply waviness on the buckling analysis by applying the equivalent homogenized properties of the composite laminate under consideration. The plate is assumed to be simply-supported on all of its four edges. The out-of-plane displacement $w(x, y)$ of the plate is assumed to be in the form of

$$w(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N A_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{2L}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{2L}\right) \quad (10)$$

where m and n are odd numbers, and A_{mn} are

Fig. 5. Laminate with waviness under pure compression

unknown coefficients to be determined. Assuming that the layup is symmetric and balanced with $D_{16} = D_{26} = 0$, the buckling load can be determined by minimizing the total potential energy Π of the plate:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi = & \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^L \left\{ D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) + 2D_{12} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) \right. \\ & \left. + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) + 4D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right) \right\} dx dy \quad (11) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^L N_x \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) dx dy \end{aligned}$$

where N_x is the applied compressive load per unit width, and D_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, 6$), are the bending stiffnesses at any location in the plate. The coupling terms D_{16} and D_{26} could be incorporated with appropriate changes in Eq. (10) at a slight increase in complexity by introducing an anisotropy factor [22]. The unknowns A_{mn} are determined by minimizing the total energy

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial A_{mn}} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Carrying out the integrations, and setting the derivative of Π with respect to A_{mn} equal to zero, leads to the generalized eigenvalue problem:

$$[\mathbf{A}]\{\mathbf{x}\} = \lambda[\mathbf{B}]\{\mathbf{x}\} \quad (13)$$

where the eigenvalue λ is the buckling load when $N_x = 1$ lbf/in is applied; the eigenvector $\{\mathbf{x}\}$ contains the constants A_{mn} of Eq. (10), and the matrices $[\mathbf{A}]$ and $[\mathbf{B}]$ contain stiffness and geometry information of the problem. Therefore, in case of a square plate ($L = L'$), the main critical buckling load is given as

$$N_{xcrit} = \frac{\pi^2 [D_{11} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) + D_{22}]}{L^2} \quad (14)$$

To compensate for the effects of transverse shear which could become important when analyzing thick laminate plates, one can write [22]

$$\bar{N}_{xcrit} = (N_{xcrit}^{-1} + (G_{xy}t)^{-1})^{-1} \quad (15)$$

where G_{xy} and t are the shear modulus and thickness of the laminate plate, respectively. Eq. (15) is only applicable to balanced and symmetric laminates. To account for the anisotropy of the laminate plate where the coupling terms D_{16} and D_{26} could not be neglected, an anisotropy factor would be considered as [22]

$$\bar{N}_{xcrit}^* = \left(1 + \frac{0.12(D_{16} + D_{26})}{\sqrt{D_{11}D_{66}}} \right)^{-1} \bar{N}_{xcrit} \quad (16)$$

3.1.2 Finite Element Modeling

Based on the formulation introduced in section 2.1, a macro was prepared using Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) enabling the users to calculate the equivalent homogenized properties of the composite laminate having wavy plies (see Fig. 6). The users will have to insert the geometry of the waviness, stiffness properties of the idealized lamina with perfectly straight fibers along with the laminates layup as the input. The output of the program would be the averaged equivalent homogenized mechanical properties of the wavy

Fig. 6. VBA program developed to obtain the equivalent homogenized properties of the laminates having wavy plies

lamina or laminates which could be used for structural analysis of the composite structures having wavy plies.

Here we consider a 20 in × 20 in square panel comprised of 88 plies $[(\pm 45_3/0_2)_3/(\pm 45_4/0_2)_2]_S$ of Carbon/Epoxy tape laminate with the lamina properties of $E_1 = 19.30$ msi , $E_2 = 1.40$ msi , $E_3 = 1.29$ msi , $G_{12} = 0.799$ msi , $G_{23} = 0.422$ msi , $G_{13} = 0.733$ msi , $\nu_{12} = 0.317$, $\nu_{13} = 0.357$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.452$. Eight different FEM cases were run, each with different waviness lengths (l_w) of 0 (laminate having plies with straight fibers), 1 in, 2 in, 4 in, 8 in, 12 in, 16 in and 20 in. The maximum height of the waviness was considered to be 0.30 in.

For the FEM, the Nastran software (SOL 105) by MSC was used. The model consisted of 1600 four-noded quadrilateral elements with 1681 nodes. The geometry, loading, and typical results obtained from FEM are shown in Figs. 5 and 7.

Fig. 7. Typical buckling results under compression

Two different approaches were considered with FEM. In the first called two-phase FEM approach, the panel was considered to be made of two different regions, regions at extremities having the properties of laminas with straight fibers and the wavy region

Table 1. Comparison of different FEM and analytical approaches for the case of the pure compression

l_w (in)	1: Two-phase FEM (lbf/in)	2: One-phase FEM (lbf/in)	3: One-phase Analytical (lbf/in)	Difference between 1 & 2 (%)	Difference between 2 & 3 (%)
0	7749	7749	8269	0	+6.7
1	7165	7055	7461	-1.5	+5.8
2	7159	7190	7627	+0.4	+6.1
4	7343	7422	7881	+1.1	+6.2
8	7530	7586	8061	+0.7	+6.3
12	7607	7652	8128	+0.6	+6.2
16	7661	7685	8162	+0.3	+6.2
20	7684	7684	8183	0	+6.5

Fig. 8. Compression buckling load reduction by waviness

in the middle of the panel with averaged reduced properties obtained from the VBA program by considering $L = l_w$ (see Fig. 6). In the second approach called one-phase FEM, the equivalent homogenized properties of the composite laminate with wavy plies were applied all over the panel. In this approach, L in the VBA program was considered to be 20 in, and the average homogenized properties were obtained for laminas with different waviness length. The buckling loads predicted by the two FEM approaches have been compared in Table 1 and Fig. 8 with those obtained from Eq. 16. In all cases and with the both FEM approaches used here, the FE-predicted buckling modes were symmetric. The highest difference between the two FEM approaches was 1.5%. The FEM results were successfully correlated to those obtained from Eq. (16) with the maximum of 6.7% deviation (see Table 1).

Fig. 9 shows the reduction in the buckling load of the panel in compression as a function of waviness parameters (l_w and h_{max}). For example, for $l_w = 2$ in and $h_{max} = 0.4$ in, one can expect ~12% reduction in the critical buckling load in compression.

Fig. 9. Effect of the waviness parameters on the critical compression buckling load of our 88-ply composite panel

3.2 Shear Case

3.2.1 Analytical Formulation

For the case of shear, we considered the same rectangular composite plate as in section 3.1 having the same waviness characteristics (see Fig. 10). The plate was loaded by a shear load N_{xy} . Therefore the total potential energy Π of the plate (Eq. 11) for the case of pure shear can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi = & \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^L \left\{ D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) + 2D_{12} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) \right. \\ & \left. + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) + 4D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right) \right\} dx dy \quad (17) \\ & - \int_0^L \int_0^L N_{xy} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right) dx dy \end{aligned}$$

Table 2. Comparison of different FEM and analytical approaches for the case of the pure shear

l_w (in)	1: Two-phase FEM (lbf/in)	2: One-phase FEM (lbf/in)	3: One-phase Analytical (lbf/in)	Difference between 1 & 2 (%)	Difference between 2 & 3 (%)
0	16974	16974	17008	0.0	+0.2
1	15881	15513	15539	-2.3	+0.2
2	15824	15808	15851	-0.1	+0.3
4	16146	16288	16321	+0.9	+0.2
8	16523	16632	16663	+0.7	+0.2
12	16685	16772	16774	+0.5	+0.0
16	16813	16840	16831	+0.2	-0.1
20	16837	16837	16866	+0.0	+0.2

Fig. 10. Laminate with waviness under pure shear

Fig. 11. Typical buckling results under pure shear

The Rayleigh-Ritz method was used to determine the buckling load. This method is set out in Timoshenko and Gere's text [23]. The out-of-plane displacement $w(x, y)$ of the plate was considered as

a polynomial-based displacement function which consists of a boundary polynomial specifying the geometric and kinematic boundary conditions, multiplied by a complete two-dimensional simple polynomial. This displacement function has been used successfully for the modeling of bilateral plate buckling problems [24,25], and can be written as

$$w(x, y) = xy(x - I)(y - I) \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{n=0}^N a_k x^m y^{N-n} \quad (18)$$

where M is the degree of a two-dimensional polynomial, a_k is the arbitrary Ritz coefficient and k is determined as

$$k = \frac{(N + I)(N + 2)}{2} - n \quad (19)$$

Fig. 11 shows the typical shear mode shape of the panel under shear loading. The edges of the plate are all simply supported. Therefore, the shear buckling load can be expressed as [26]

$$N_{xycrit} = \frac{\pi^2 k_s}{L^2} (D_{11} D_{22}^3)^{0.25} \quad (20)$$

where k_s is the shear buckling factor and for our specific layup, it was determined to be equal to 12.8.

3.2.2 Finite Element Modeling

For the FEM, the same models as those introduced in section 3.1.2 were used by Nastran software. The nodes located on the edge lines were loaded under pure shear. The comparison of the analytical Rayleigh-Ritz method with the results of the two

Fig. 12. Shear buckling load reduction by waviness

Fig. 13. Effect of the waviness parameters on the critical shear buckling load of our 88-ply composite panel

different FEM approaches which were introduced in section 3.1.2, has been shown in Table 2 and Fig. 12. As it can be seen, there is an excellent agreement between the two FEM approaches (worst deviation is -2.3%). Fig. 13 shows the reduction in the buckling load of the panel under pure shear as a function of waviness parameters (l_w and h_{max}).

4 Summary and Conclusions

The explicit forms of the stiffness for a laminate containing out-of-plane fiber waviness were derived. The results were in excellent agreement with those obtained from complex M-FEM of Garnich *et al.* [17]. The reduction of the lamina stiffness E_x was found to be 3%, 10%, 40% and 70% for plies having 1%, 2%, 5% and 10% waviness, respectively. These equivalent homogenized properties were then used for the compression and shear stability analysis of the composite panels having fiber waviness. For a 20 in \times 20 in square panel comprised of 88 plies $[(\pm 45_3/0_2)_3/(\pm 45_4/0_2)_2]_S$ of Carbon/Epoxy tape laminate having waviness parameters of $l_w/L = 0.1$

and $a_{max}/l_w = 0.075$, it was found that the reduction of the stiffness will lead to 8% and 7% decrease in the buckling load for the case of pure compression and pure shear, respectively.

Two different FE modeling approaches were selected and their results were compared with those of closed form analytical formulations. It was also shown that the results are in close agreement with each other with the maximum deviation of 6.7% and 0.3% for the case of pure compression and pure shear, respectively. We also found that for thick laminates, the effects of the local changes of the fiber volume fraction which is caused by the waviness (i.e., changes on the local ply stiffness and the waviness geometry), don't have considerable effect on the compression and shear buckling loads (results not shown). Therefore, to find the effective stiffness of a laminate having ply waviness, one need to first measure the waviness parameters (l_w/L and a_{max}/l_w) and then use the formulations introduced in section 2.1 (VBA tool shown in Fig. 6). Once the equivalent homogenized properties of the laminate having waviness were determined, they can be used subsequently for the stability analysis using the analytical formulations introduced in section 3. Although the waviness is usually local, however, it would be accurate enough if the homogenized stiffness values be applied all over the panel instead of considering the panel with several regions with or without waviness.

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